

A MODIFIED IOSIPESCU TEST FOR ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITE PANELS

Jonas M. Neumeister and L. Niklas Melin

Department of Solid Mechanics, Royal Institute of Technology (KTH)

SE – 100 44 Stockholm, Sweden

ABSTRACT – The Iosipescu (V-notched beam) shear test for in-plane shear properties of composite panels (ASTM D-5379) is modified with respect to specimen geometry. The ASTM standard prescribes V-notches with 90° opening angle, while the resulting stress field in the test region strongly depends on the material anisotropy, a feature present in many composite materials. Thus, the test performance depends both on actual material properties and on material orientation relative the test region. Here, a variable notch opening angle is proposed to accommodate both material anisotropy and orientation. The recommended notch opening is determined through a simple rescaling operation based on the ratio of Young's moduli along the two the axes of orthotropy, *viz.* $\lambda = E_2/E_1$. By this procedure, the non-uniformity of the stress profile in the test region is substantially reduced, and ideally approaches the one which can be accomplished in an isotropic material. The validity of this approach is investigated numerically through an FE-analysis of a strongly anisotropic (i.e. uniaxially reinforced) composite for a range of notch opening angles. Further, experiments on such a composite are performed, both with standard (90°-) notches, the here recommended notch openings, and additionally both wider and narrower notch opening angles those suggested. Moreover, the material is tested in two configurations: with the fibers along the test region (which requires a narrower notch opening), and across the test region (using a wider notch opening). Employing an optical technique, whole-field strain measurements are performed during testing of all test setups which confirm the results from the numerical study. For both test configurations, the best results are obtained with the here proposed improvements, whereas the highest strengths still are obtained with the fibers bridging the test region. However, stress levels attained before first cracking occurs are increased by more than 30% with the recommended modifications. Finally, using the whole field measurements, in-situ stress-strain responses are extracted from all tests, initial shear moduli are reported, and compared to values from ordinary strain gage measurements. It is once again confirmed that measuring constitutive properties of composites in shear is a difficult and intricate issue.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Ideally, a well designed test should produce a well defined and uniform state of stress in the test region. The most widely used test method for determining in-plane shear properties of composite panels is the Iosipescu (or V-notched beam) test, ASTM D-5379[1]. One issue concerning composite panels is that they often exhibit substantially anisotropic properties, and to an extent which varies from one tested material to the next. As a consequence, the stress state in the test region of a Iosipescu specimen depends on the material tested and its orientation[2-10]. The ASTM standard prescribes V-notches with a 90° opening angle. For a strongly anisotropic material, as e.g. a uniaxially fiber reinforced composite, three different strength values are reported: one with the fibers oriented along the test region (here called the 0°-orientation) and levels for both first cracking (emanating from the notch roots) and peak force with the fibers running across the projected failure zone (the 90°-orientation) [3,4,9,10]. In the latter configuration, multiple cracks may often be observed in the specimen center prior to ultimate failure[8,9]. Further, the first cracking alters the specimen geometry in what seems to be a favourable way, but which also indicates that the test design is not optimal[8,9]. Also the loading of the specimen is a delicate issue: clamping, contact loading and undesired bending and twisting further impair the nominal stress state[9,10]. From a continuum point-of-view, shear stresses and shear moduli are equal along two perpendicular directions, i.e. $\tau_{12} = \tau_{21}$ and $G_{12} = G_{21}$, but experimentally the results may differ substantially[3,4,9]. This is attributed to the non-uniform stress fields in the test regions and the distinctly different failure modes for the two configurations[6,9,10].

METHOD AND ANALYSIS

The Iosipescu test was originally devised for shear tests of (isotropic) metals, for which a notch opening of $2\theta = 110^\circ$ was found optimal with respect to stress uniformity (at a sharp notch, the mode II singularity vanishes for $2\theta > 102.6^\circ$)[2]. The purpose of this work is to modify the geometry of an Iosipescu composite specimen, in order to achieve a more uniform stress field in the test region, by varying the notch opening angle (2θ). It has been demonstrated, both numerically[4,6-9] and experimentally[5,9], that the highest strains arise at different locations depending on the material anisotropy and its orientation. Thus, the appropriate notch opening must depend on material properties and testing configuration. Generally, the resulting stress state in a plane specimen loaded with boundary tractions is independent of its elastic properties only for isotropic materials (described by E and ν), otherwise it depends on its anisotropic elastic properties (C_{ijkl}). Specifically for orthotropic materials, the stress state in a plane problem depends on two (combinations of) elastic constants[11], here called

$$\lambda = \frac{E_2}{E_1} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho = \frac{\sqrt{E_1 E_2}}{G_{12}} - \sqrt{\nu_{12} \nu_{21}} \quad (1ab)$$

where 1 and 2 denote the axes of orthotropy. Note that for an isotropic material, both these constants are unity, while for a cubic material only $\lambda = 1$. Here, a scheme of lengthwise rescaling the orthotropic specimen by a factor $1/\sqrt[4]{\lambda}$ is employed[11]. This transforms the anisotropic boundary value problem into an equivalent one with a material of cubic symmetry which, in turn, often can be described with solutions for isotropic materials with good accuracy (i.e. independent of elastic properties) since the dependence on ρ is usually much weaker. Using the original specimen shape as a reference (with $\tan(55^\circ) = 1.43$), the notch in an optimal orthotropic specimen should then have an opening angle given by

$$\tan\theta = \frac{1.43}{\sqrt[4]{\lambda}} \quad \text{where} \quad \lambda = \frac{E_y}{E_x} \quad (2ab)$$

Note that here, the directions and moduli in λ are defined in reference to the specimen as shown in Figure 1 (i.e. x denotes the fiber direction for the 90° -configuration, and conversely the transverse direction for the 0° -configuration). Consequently, depending on the material orientation (whether $\lambda > 1$ or $\lambda < 1$) both sharper and shallower notches (than 110°) are recommended, see Figures 1bc.

Figure 1. The Iosipescu specimen with a) ASTM standard notch ($2\theta = 90^\circ$), b) sharper notch opening for the 0° -test configuration, and c) wider notch opening for the 90° -test configuration. (Fiber directions are indicated)

The effects of varying the notch opening angle (2θ) are studied numerically and experimentally in this study. An FE-analysis of the stress state for strongly anisotropic composite for both standard geometry and different opening angles for both test configurations is presented in the next section. The same geometries are investigated experimentally in a newly built Iosipescu fixture. Optical whole field strain measurements are performed on all specimens and compared to FE-results. Strains are also monitored using conventional strain gages and moduli are determined or estimated from the different measurements.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The Iosopescu specimen is modelled in the FE-code ANSYS as a homogeneous orthotropic body under plane stress conditions. The material parameters used are presented in the table below.

Table 1. Orthotropic elastic properties for a uniaxial carbon fiber/epoxy composite (by supplier)

Young's moduli [GPa]	Shear moduli [GPa]	Poisson's ratios [-]
$E_1 = 140, E_2 = 10 (E_3 = 10)$	$G_{12} = 5.2 (= G_{13}, G_{23} = 3.8)$	$\nu_{12} = 0.30 (= \nu_{13}, \nu_{23} = \nu_{32} = 0.50, \nu_{21} = \nu_{31} = 0.02)$

(values in parantheses are not used in the FE-calculations)

Only elastic behavior was considered in the FE-analysis. However, it should be noted that in strength tests on the material studied here, the elastic shear limit is exceeded and considerable irreversible deformation is encountered prior to ultimate levels[3,6,9]. Another issue studied numerically is the notch root radius. A general rule in testing of material bulk properties is to avoid sharp corners. On the other hand, a smooth radius defining the end of the test region, produces a vanishing shear stress there, which has to build up to its the nominal value over a length related to the notch root radius. Thus, a sharper notch root might be motivated by stress uniformity arguments. For this purpose, the specimen was modelled with one smooth (radius $r = 1.3$ mm) and one sharp notch (see Figure 2) while maintaining the nominal test region length (length $l = 12$ mm). This also implies that the notch flanks are positioned slightly different relative the test region among the two notches, and that this difference is the more pronounced the larger notch opening angle is used.

Figure 2. The FE-model geometries for the modified Iosipescu specimens with one sharp and one rounded notch. The clamping region is indicated on the right half of the specimen.

The boundary conditions imposed were prescribed displacements in the y -direction in the clamping regions, while each clamped region was free to move in the x -direction to avoid normal net forces in the test region. Nominal loading was imposed by a relative displacement in the y -direction between the two clamped regions, see Figure 2.

The resulting shear stress fields in the test region for all investigated geometries and both test configurations are shown in Figure 3. Since the test region is bordered by one rounded and one sharp notch, the stress profiles are not symmetrical as they would be with two identical notches. To compare the effects of the two different notches, the stress profiles are normalized with their average shear stress in the respective half of the test region, and these presented (half) profiles should be very close to those obtained when using two identical notches. (The shear stresses from the actual FE-calculations here are of course continuous in the center).

Clearly, the notch root geometry affects the stress profiles. Particularly in the 0° -configuration the build-up of shear stresses from the rounded notch root is slow: they reach a maximum in the specimen center but never approach a constant stress state. Further, they are essentially independent of the notch opening angle (2θ). Studying instead the profiles for the sharp notch, the effects of varying θ are clearly visible: the whole profile becomes markedly more uniform as θ decreases, and for a sufficiently low θ , singular shear stresses arise at the sharp notch root as one would expect. This can

be understood in terms of the orthotropic rescaling mentioned above: local effects and perturbations, such as e.g. effects of notch root geometry, carry through over larger distances in the stiff direction compared to the weak direction, an anisotropic Saint Venant's effect.

Figure 3. Shear stress profiles for different notch opening angles used in a) the 0°- and b) the 90°-test configuration. Stress profiles are normalized with their average value in each half the test region, to the left near the rounded notch, and to the right near the sharp notch.

In the 90°-configuration, effects of the notch root radius on the stress profile are much less pronounced (although singular stresses arise at the sharp notch). Instead, the notch opening angle 2θ dictates the shape of the stress profile. Indeed, the most uniform profile is obtained for an opening of $2\theta = 141^\circ$ as predicted by eq. 2a. Finally, it is seen that for both test configurations the standard geometry of $2\theta = 90^\circ$ gives the poorest results in terms of stress uniformity: stresses (and thus strains) are either about 10-15% higher or lower than nominal in the center of the test region (where e.g. strain gages would be applied).

EXPERIMENTAL

A panel consisting of 32 layers of a uniaxially oriented Fiberdux HTA/6376C carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg with a nominal panel thickness of 4.35 mm was used for the present investigation. The reported elastic properties are given in table 1. Using a water jet cutting machine, specimens were manufactured with notch openings of $2\theta = [64^\circ, 71^\circ, 80^\circ, 90^\circ]$ (for the 0°-configuration) and $2\theta = [90^\circ, 110^\circ, 125^\circ, 141^\circ, 150^\circ]$ for the 90°-configuration).

Figure 4. The newly built Iosipescu fixture. Note the clamping mechanism and base part suspension.

Particularly the assumed optimal opening angles (71° and 141°) were determined from eqs. (2ab) based on manufacturer provided data giving $\lambda = 16$ or $1/16$, which were later revised to the properties in table 1. (With $\lambda = 14$ or $1/14$ those angles would be 73° and 140° , i.e. a very minor modification). The resulting notch root radius was about 0.5 mm. For the shear tests performed here, a new Iosipescu fixture was designed and built. Novel features are an improved clamping mechanism and a suspension of the fixture base half which is compliant in the x -direction to circumvent net normal forces during clamping and testing, see Figure 4.

STRAIN RESULTS

Whole field strain measurements were performed on every specimen geometry and test configuration. An Aramis GOM mbH (Germany) system was used for the Digital Speckle Photography (DSP), which follows an speckle image (spray paint), applied to the surface, during deformation with a CCD camera. With an image correlation algorithm, deformed and undeformed subimages of typically 15×15 pixels are compared to determine displacements fields. In-plane strain fields are obtained by differentiating the displacements, with an accuracy of below 0.1% in strain. In the figures below, shear strain fields at loads close to failure loads are presented. Figure 5 shows the known deficiencies of the standard Iosipescu specimen geometry: non-uniform stresses with peaks either at the notch roots or in the center.

Figure 5. DSP recorded shear strain fields for the standard geometry (90° -notch) at loads just before first cracking/failure for a) the 90° -configurations at $\tau_{nom} = 68$ MPa, and b) the 0° -configuration at $\tau_{nom} = 59$ MPa. Note the non-uniform shear strain profiles, whose levels are shown (in degrees, $^\circ$) as $\epsilon_{xy} = \gamma/2$.

Figure 6. (continued on next page)

Figure 6. DSP recorded shear strain fields for the 0° -configuration at loads just before failure for notch opening angles of $2\theta =$ a) 64° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 53$ MPa, b) 71° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 65$ MPa, c) 71° with sharp notches at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 56$ MPa, and d) 80° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 48$ MPa (strains $\varepsilon_{xy} = \gamma/2$ are given in degrees, $^\circ$)

In Figures 6 and 7 the corresponding strain fields close to failure/first cracking loads are shown for all other tested notch opening angles. Note how the narrowing and the opening, respectively, of the notch opening angles compared to the standard geometry, improves the strain uniformity conditions.

Figure 7. DSP recorded shear strain fields for the 90° -configuration at loads just before first cracking for notch opening angles of $2\theta =$ a) 110° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 87$ MPa, b) 125° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 92$ MPa, c) 141° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 97$ MPa, and d) 150° at $\tau_{\text{nom}} = 96$ MPa (strains $\varepsilon_{xy} = \gamma/2$ are given in degrees, $^\circ$).

Figure 8. DSP measured shear strain profiles along the test region in all specimens from Figures 6 and 7 at loads close to failure/first cracking for a) the 0°-configuration, and b) 90°-configuration.

In Figure 9, the average shear strain along the test region (as e.g. from the profiles in Figures 5, 6 and 7) is plotted versus the applied nominal stress which gives an indication of the composite constitutive behavior in shear, and of its shear modulus G_{12} . However, these results should be used with caution: They are obtained from DSP shear measurements from the specimen front face. However, strains can differ notably between the front and back face due to undesired bending, twisting, etc. The recommended procedure is to use the average shear strain level obtained from e.g. strain gages on both faces.

Figure 9. DSP measured stress strain responses in shear for all specimens during the loading sequence for a) the 0°-configuration, and b) 90°-configuration. (The shear strains are mutually off-set by 0.2% and 0.5%, respectively).

In Table 2, measured/estimated shear moduli are reported based on both methods of strain measurements for the various specimens. Note that it is difficult to make other than qualitative statements about the precise value of G_{12} .

Table 2. Shear moduli values (G_{12}) from DSP and strain gage measurements for all specimens

G_{12} [GPa]	0°-configuration					90°-configuration				
angle $2\theta =$	64°	71°	(71°) ¹	80°	90°	90°	110°	125°	141°	150°
DSP ²	5.63	5.62	5.54	4.94	4.71	6.16	5.90	5.61	6.17	6.05
Strain gages ³			6.84 ³		5.32 ^{3,4}	6.48 ^{3,4}			6.74 ³	

- 1) Sharpened notch
- 2) DSP strains are measured only on specimen front face
- 3) Strain gages are applied on both faces
- 4) Strains from test region center, not compensated for inhomogenous fields

STRENGTH RESULTS

The in-plane composite stress-strain response in shear and the corresponding strength (along the axes of orthotropy) should be independent of the which principal direction is oriented aligned with the test region, i.e. independent of test configuration. It is well known that this is far from true. True values for both strength and modulus are difficult to assess, and different tests methods give contradicting results. Indeed, this is one of the main motivations for the present work. Regarding material bulk strength, it is generally accepted that most test methods give results on the low side since failure most often is initiated locally, i.e. at stress concentrators such as notches and/or by other undesired loading conditions. Hence, it is understood that the test giving the highest reading prior to cracking (or other failure occurrences) is the most accurate one since this is the level the material is known for certain to have withstood. However, as the material strength often is limited by local effects, the test that gives the lowest such level may be used as a conservative value. Here, stresses for catastrophic failure for the the 0°-configuration (which is the lowest value), and for first cracking and ultimate transferred stress during the test are given for the 90°-configuration (these are the higher values, and several load peaks may be observed after first cracking). All strength values are given i Table 3, they are average values from at least four specimens, and the observed scatter among each test setup was quite low.

Table 3. Shear strength values ($\hat{\tau}_{12}$) for all tests (each averaged from at least four specimens)

$\hat{\tau}_{12}$ [MPa] for	0°-configuration					90°-configuration				
angle $2\theta=$	64°	71°	(71°) ¹	80°	90°	90°	110°	125°	141°	150°
first crack	57.8	61.7	(50.3) ¹	56.8	60.7	76.6	91.4	94.8	103.6	94.6
ultimate	-	-	-	-	-	125.4 ²	116.7 ²	109.5 [*]	104.6 ³	105.9 ⁴

- 1) Sharpened notch
- 2) Multiple cracking and major damage in test region, load carried in tension by the fibers
- 3) Tests terminated due to excessive specimen deformation
- 4) Failure by crushing in gripping zone (* - one specimen)

Encouraging is that for both configurations, the highest values (bold in Table 3) were obtained for the proposed notch geometry (eq. 2a). The improvement (compared to a standard 90°-notch) is the largest in the 90°-configuration. For the optimized notch geometry (141°) in the 90°-configuration, the load could not be increased substantially after first (and second) cracking (and similarly for the two other wider notch openings, 125° and 150°), while the two narrowest notch openings resulted in excessive multiple cracks in the test region, visible rotation of the fibers bridging the ligament, which then experienced tensile loading, i.e. not representative for bulk material behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

It is here shown, both numerically and experimentally, that in-plane shear testing of anisotropic composite panels can be substantially improved by modifying the notch opening angle. The adjustment, according to a very simple formula (eq. 2), only requires knowledge of the Young's moduli in the two principal directions, i.e. material properties which are much easier to aquire (or to calculate/estimate from constituent properties) than are shear properties. For both configurations, the strength results are improved, with the 90°-configuration still giving the highest strength readings but also the highest relative improvement. The 90°-configuration is more forgiving when it comes to imperfections always present in experiments. Presumably, failure in the 0°-configuration still originates at the notch roots, probably due to such imperfections and thus resulting undesired high stresses there[9,11]. Further, stress profiles in the 0°-configuration are more affected by the notch root geometry: with a rounded notch, effects of notch opening are diminished which is also observed as a lower effect on obtained strength values. The FE-calculated tendency of more uniform stress profiles with sharper notches is also confirmed with the DSP measurements, while the sharper notch, however, reduces the experimentally attainable strengths, but not dramatically. The 90°-configuration widens the notch region by a factor $1/\sqrt[4]{\lambda}$ which for a uniaxial, i.e. strongly anisotropic composite as used here can imply a doubling of the notch region size, which then extends well into the gripping part of the

fixture. Then, arising stresses in the clamping region become an issue: higher clamping forces and higher attained loading levels over a reduced clamping region. Indeed, for the widest notch openings, crushing in the gripping section was observed prior to ultimate net section failure. However, in practice such composites are rarely used, commonly used composites are both less anisotropic, they are reinforced in several directions which would give less extreme notch openings, and thus larger gripping zones and moreover it reduces the tendency to crushing failure. Recommended based on the results found here is 1) to modify the notch opening angle according to eqs. (2ab), 2) to use the 90°-configuration when studying the stress-strain behavior at higher loads, 3) to use the 0°-configuration for assessing strengths under the most unfavourable conditions, and 4) to use sharper notches (preferably in both configurations) to measure elastic shear moduli.

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